

Traditional Approach paving ways for Modern Approaches

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The 'North East' of India is one of the most diversified region that has been encompassing a huge amount of bioresources of our Nation 'India'. With the unique topology and climatic conditions the region is blessed with a huge amount of flora and fauna ranging in every strata.

The diversified flora and fauna utilization is seen among the different tribes and communities residing in North-East. The North Eastern States of India with its aboriginal tribes and communities have an excellent understanding of the traditional approaches, approaches that have been utilized in different fields for its benefits, for instance to eradicate a variety of ailments and diseases. The tribes and communities with their traditional medicine extraction procedures although needs some refinement while applying and targeting modern medical approaches but the traditional "tribe-community" approach will help Mankind in setting a solid foundation for exploration. With the ever increasing losses to health diseases, never ending disease conditions and toxicity of modern medicines the need of the hour is to rightly explore and open doors to traditional and modern future approaches simultaneously.

Keywords: North-East, tribes and communities, traditional medicine, diseases